

Gamma rays from fast black-hole winds

Chris Karwin

Clemson University, Clemson, South Carolina 29634, USA

Black-hole winds from active galactic nuclei (AGN), also known as ultra-fast outflows (UFOs), are thought to contribute significantly to galaxy evolution and feedback, namely, the evolution of the bulge, the star formation, and the black hole growth [1]. The outflowing gas of a UFO may generate shock waves through interactions with the surrounding interstellar medium, which may subsequently produce γ -ray emission [2, 3, 4]. In this work we search for the γ -ray emission from UFOs using data collected by the Large Area Telescope (LAT; [5]) on board the *Fermi Gamma-ray Space Telescope*. Models of the γ -ray emission from UFOs [2, 4] show them to be weak emitters, with γ -ray luminosities of $\approx 10^{40}$ erg s $^{-1}$, which explains why UFOs have not yet been detected by the LAT. Here, we adopt a different strategy and search for the collective γ -ray emission from a sample of UFOs using a stacking technique.

Figure 1: Stacked TS profile for the sample of UFOs. The color scale indicates the TS, and the plus sign indicates the location of the maximum value, with a TS = 30.1 (5.1σ). Significance contours (for 2 degrees of freedom) are overlaid on the plot showing the 68%, 90%, and 99% confidence levels, corresponding to Δ TS = 2.30, 4.61, and 9.21, respectively.

Our sample consists of all nearby ($z < 0.1$) UFOs with a mildly relativistic wind velocity ($v > 0.1c$). The stacking technique we employ has been developed previously and has been successfully employed for multiple studies, i.e. upper limits on dark matter interactions [6], detection of the extragalactic background light [7], extreme blazars [8], and star-forming galaxies [9]. We evaluate the significance of each source using the test statistic (TS), which is defined as $TS = -2\log(L_0/L)$, where L_0 is the likelihood for the null hypothesis (i.e. no gamma rays

emitted from the UFO source), and L is the likelihood for the alternative hypothesis (i.e. γ -rays emitted from the UFO source). 2D TS profiles are generated for the spectral parameters of each UFO source. We scan photon indices from -1 to -3.3 with a spacing of 0.1 and total integrated photon flux (between 1 – 800 GeV) from 10^{-13} to 10^{-9} ph cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$ with 40 logarithmically spaced bins. The TS profiles for all sources are added to obtain the stacked profile, which gives the statistical significance for the combined signal.

The stacked profile for our UFO sample is shown in Figure 1. The maximum TS is 30.1 (5.1σ), corresponding to a best-fit index of -2.1 ± 0.3 and a best-fit photon flux (1 – 800 GeV) of $2.5_{-0.9}^{+1.5} \times 10^{-11}$ ph cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$. The 68%, 90%, and 99% significance contours are overlaid on the map, and as can be seen the spectral parameters are well constrained.

We repeat the analysis with a sample of 20 low redshift ($z < 0.1$) radio-quiet AGN that do not have UFOs. The sources were selected from the samples of [10] and [11] for which no UFO was found. The sample of [10] is based on absorption features, while the sample of [11] uses the excess variance method. No signal is detected from the control sample, with a maximum TS of 1.1 . Using the profile likelihood method and a photon index of -2.0 , the upper limit on the flux (1 – 800 GeV) at the 95% confidence level is 8.8×10^{-12} ph cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$. We have also shown that the γ -ray emission observed in the UFOs is a factor of ~ 40 larger than what we would expect for star-formation activity, and that it's highly unlikely the UFO emission results from weak jets. This supports the interpretation of the γ -ray emission being due to the outflow rather than other processes in AGN.

The γ -ray luminosity from UFOs is predicted to scale with the AGN bolometric luminosity. To test this relationship we calculate the stacked profile in bins of bolometric luminosity. Additionally, we calculated the stacked profile in terms of efficiency, defined as $\epsilon_{\text{Bol}} = L_\gamma/L_{\text{Bol}}$. Results for this are shown in Figure 2. Indeed, we do find a scaling relation, and we measure the best-fit efficiency to be $(3.2 \pm 1.5) \times 10^{-4}$.

The physical model for the UFO SED is calculated by assuming that the γ -ray emission is dominated by hadronic processes resulting from diffusive shock acceleration. The observed γ -ray SED indicates a firm detection of cosmic ray (CR) protons with energies reaching at least as high as $\approx 10^{12-13}$ eV. Within our hadronic emission model we derive that on average the forward shock has traveled ~ 20 – 300 pc (~ 65 – 980 light years) away from the supermassive black hole and that the maximum energy of protons accelerated at the forward shock is $\approx 10^{17}$ eV. This makes AGN winds a potential source of CRs with energies beyond the 'knee' of the CR spectrum (i.e., 3×10^{15} eV) and also likely contributors to the IceCube neutrino flux [13].

Figure 2: γ -ray luminosity versus bolometric luminosity. The black data points result from stacking in γ -ray luminosity, and the uncertainty in the x-axis corresponds to the bin widths. The grey dash-dot vertical lines show the value used to divide the bins. The solid green line shows the best-fit resulting from stacking in efficiency, with the green band showing the 1σ confidence level. For reference, the blue lines show a range of efficiencies within roughly an order of magnitude of the best fit. The orange bar shows the average one-sided uncertainty in individual measurements of AGN bolometric luminosity. We also overlay the predicted efficiency derived from [12] (dashed purple line).

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Short CV

2013: BSc, Physics, University of Colorado, Colorado Springs, USA
 2017: MSc, Physics, University of California, Irvine, USA
 2019: PhD, Physics, University of California, Irvine, USA
 2019-present: Postdoctoral Fellow, Clemson University, USA